

DURABILITY OF SODA—LIME—SILICATE GLASSES. PART IV

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A detailed study of the phenomenon of the tendency of the H_2SO_4 value of glass powder to give lower H_2SO_4 value after a few determinations on exposure has been made. The successive residual H_2SO_4 values of chilled glass is found to be distinctly higher than the corresponding values for the same glasses after annealing.

In part I of this series of papers it was pointed out that if the glass powder, left after the determination of sulphuric acid value, be kept exposed to atmosphere under moist condition, it again gave sulphuric acid value of a lower magnitude (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 477). Again, in connection with our study of the effect of annealing on chemical durability of glass, it has been found that the above tendency is also more or less pronounced, depending, however, upon the thickness of the glass mass and the total surface exposed by it (Sen, Chowdhury and Das-Gupta, *ibid.*, 1949, 26, 353, 379). The present paper embraces a detailed study of the above observed phenomenon.

From the experimental portion it will be evident that soda-lime-silicate glass, whether chilled or annealed, when subjected successively to powder test (Peddle, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1920, 4, 3, 299), after intervals of 24 hours each, gives sulphuric acid values of descending magnitude and up to a restricted number of times. In order to avoid confusion, these values have been designated as residual sulphuric acid values. On an average, nine or ten such treatments are necessary, when the last residual sulphuric acid value becomes almost zero. From a comparative study, it is found that the successive residual sulphuric acid values of chilled glasses are distinctly higher than the corresponding values for the same glasses after annealing (Table III).

The effect of successive heat treatments on soda-lime-silicate glass is also interesting. Thus, the annealed glass powder, which ceases to give residual sulphuric acid value, if it be again subjected to annealing temperature for a specified time and then cooled slowly, it gives a series of residual sulphuric acid values. If this be repeated a number of times, different series of residual sulphuric acid values are obtained (Table IV). In each case, however, the annealing was done at 500° for five hours.

EXPERIMENTAL

In order to get measures in respect of successive residual sulphuric acid values, two different series of 'like' glasses were prepared. These glasses were founded and plained as usual in Morgan crucibles. In each case the glass was chilled rapidly so as to avoid the favourable effect of slow cooling. Table I shows the purity of the ingredients used, and Table II, the % composition of the batch mixtures. Each specimen was

subjected to powder test and the residual powder was allowed to remain moist and exposed to atmosphere in a glass case for 24 hours. This was again heated with distilled water (100 c.c.) at 80° for an hour. The liquid was then filtered and the residue thoroughly washed with distilled water, the runnings being added to the filtrate. The filtrate was titrated, as usual, with sulphuric acid and the residual glass was again kept exposed to atmosphere under identical conditions for 24 hours. The exposed product was next treated with water as above. Operations like alternate exposure and water digestion were repeated a number of times, till the powders ceased to give any residual sulphuric acid value. These results have been included in Table III.

TABLE I

Materials.	SiO ₂ .	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃ .	CaO.	MgO.	Na ₂ CO ₃ ,	NaCl, etc.	Loss
Sand	98.9%	0.2%	0.2%	Slight trace	Slight trace	...	...	0.5%
Lime	3.1	0.9	2.1	65.3%	0.2%	...	...	...
Soda ash ...	...	—	...	Slight trace	Slight trace	96.8	Slight	3.1

TABLE II

Series.	Batch No.	Percentage composition		
		SiO ₂	Na ₂ O.	CaO.
A	1	73	15	12
C	17	74	16	10

TABLE III

Batch No.	Condition of glass.	S.A.V.	Duration (in days) after which the residual H ₂ SO ₄ values determined											
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	Chilled ...	279.8	118.5	99.6	72	44.4	32.7	21.6	11.6	7.9	2.3	0.8	Nil	Nil
	Annealed	235	116	60.5	41.6	35.3	15.1	12.6	8.2	4.1	0.5	Nil	Nil	Nil
17	Chilled ...	582	175.1	81.4	69.3	51.9	40.3	31.1	18.5	12.7	9.6	2.7	0.9	Nil
	Annealed ...	506	167.3	72.6	56.4	42.3	34.3	26.2	16.1	10.3	3.5	1.2	Nil	Nil

It is thus evident from Table III that in each case, the tendency towards giving residual sulphuric acid value ceases after the lapse of 11 days. Prolonged exposure does not exert any opposite effect. This was tested with two samples (No. 1, annealed and No. 17, chilled), obtained on the 12th day. Each was exposed moist for a further period of one month. No positive result could be obtained in any case.

In order to follow the effect of repeated heat treatments on glass, the residual powder (batch No. 17, annealed), obtained on the 12th day, was again annealed at 500° for 5 hours. The annealed mass was subjected, as before, to powder test for a number of successive days, till the residual sulphuric acid value was nil. In each case the interval between any two experiments were exactly 24 hours. The powder was again annealed and the determination of residual sulphuric acid value was continued. This was continued for 2 months and the results have been incorporated in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Duration (days).	Residual S. A. V.	Duration (days).	Residual S. A. V.	Duration (days).	Residual S. A. V.
13	*	29	2.1	45	*
14	127	30	*	46	28.2
15	22.1	31	48.4	47	6.05
16	18.1	32	22.1	48	Nil
17	6.5	33	12.1	49	*
18	Nil	34	Nil	50	28.2
19	*	35	*	51	4.2
20	54.4	36	34.2	52	Nil
21	24.2	37	24.2	53	*
22	18.1	38	12.1	54	16.1
23	16.1	39	3.2	55	6.05
24	4.03	40	Nil	56	Nil
25	*	41	*	57	*
26	76.7	42	40.3	58	16.1
27	28.2	43	10.01	59	7.2
28	14.2	44	5.0	60	Nil

* Indicates annealing. S. A. V. indicates sulphuric acid value.

DISCUSSION

It is a fact that a chilled glass shows a distinctly lower resistivity than the same glass after annealing. It is considered that this increased durability is due to a structural change, which brings about strengthening of the bond between the alkali ion and the anionic network (Williams and Weyl, *Glass Ind.*, 1945, 26, 275, 325). From our findings, however, we cannot subscribe entirely to the above views. For, if annealing were

responsible for strengthening the forces which hold the alkali ions in glass, no residual sulphuric acid values should have been obtained. Secondly, there can hardly be any justification for the development of successive residual sulphuric acid values, when the glass is subjected to repeated heat treatments within the annealing temperature range. The problem becomes more complicated when it is found that there is an appreciable difference, in respect of durability, between the lump and the powdered glass from the same melt, although both may be annealed simultaneously under identical conditions. In the former case the sulphuric acid value is appreciably lower than that of the latter (Sen, Chowdhury and Das-Gupta, Part III, *loc. cit.*).

The tendency towards increased concentration of alkali at the surface is uniformly more with the powdered glass, and from Table IV, it will be clear that annealing tends to increase this tendency. This, conclusion, then, is just the opposite of what has been stated above. It appears therefore that there are some other factors responsible for this different behaviour. It is proposed to put forward our views after we have collected further data in this line.

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